

PROBLEMS OF FORMATION OF THE ACCOUNTING SYSTEM IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: All the activities of the state are connected with finance. Their importance has especially increased in connection with the acquisition of state sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan and when the society focused on the formation of a market economy, free movement of goods, services and financial resources, support for competition and freedom of economic activity. Constitutional recognition and State protection of all forms of property have become more important than ever.

Keywords: employee, financial relations, financial reporting, organizational support, statistics, control, audit.

Introduction.The process of formation and development of various organizational and legal forms of agricultural enterprises in the conditions of transition to market relations requires the availability of objective information about the production costs and the processes of forming the cost of production, which is reflected through accounting.

In this regard, the role of accounting as a means of controlling the rational use of production resources of agricultural enterprises is being strengthened.

The transition from command-and-control methods and forms of regulation of

economic life to economic ones requires bringing into action the whole variety of factors that have a direct impact on the effectiveness of management.

The command and administrative management system, focused only on the implementation of the plan, significantly hindered the development of accounting as an information basis for management. Under these conditions, national economic plans were carried out at any cost, and the importance of important indicators of economic activity of enterprises, such as the cost of production, profitability, and production efficiency, was underestimated.

The painful process of transition to market relations, when the national economy in all its directions is characterized by a large commodity deficit and there is no real competition between enterprises and there are a large number of monopolistic enterprises, orient commodity producers to increase the efficiency of production due to unlimited price increases.

Therefore, enterprises lose any incentive to increase the profitability of production due to its intensification. However, the real reserves for improving production efficiency lie not in the sphere of distribution relations, but in the sphere of production.

At the present stage of the development of agricultural production, the availability of accounting information becomes an important condition for effective management. At the same time, the whole concept of intensification changes significantly. Intensification becomes the most important factor for the survival of economic entities. With a developed market, non-intensive agricultural enterprises are doomed to be displaced.

The development of genuine entrepreneurship lies in the search for and mobilization of reserves to increase the efficiency of agricultural production on the way to its intensification.

Further improvement of accounting in these conditions, first of all, should be aimed at optimizing the information support for managing these processes.

The organization of accounting is always determined by the social, economic and organizational and technical conditions of economic activity.

At the present time, these conditions are characterized by a transition to a market economy, in particular, the strengthening of private ownership of the means of production and the rejection of the administrative-command system.

The specific conditions of Uzbekistan are rooted in the acquisition of state sovereignty, which allows it to choose its own path of development towards the market, when instead of a sharp break in the previous socio-economic relations and landslide privatization, gradual transformations are carried out using some elements of state regulation. In particular, private ownership of land and its sale are completely excluded. Organizational and technical changes in agriculture consist in the refusal of Uzbekistan from the monoculture of cotton, while maintaining its leading role in the agriculture of the republic and in the development of production, for deep processing of cotton. In order for the organization and methodology of accounting to fully meet the requirements of a market economy, it is necessary to predict the future patterns of economic structures and the actual types of agricultural enterprises in the future.

Multiculturalism is usually inherent in the transition period from one socio-economic system to another, when the old struggles for its preservation, and the new

for its formation. Modern transformations also require a transition period, which can be long and difficult. It has a variety of structures from collective farms to joint-stock companies of the capitalist type.

As the study shows, before the independence of the republic, for many years, the most important indicators of production efficiency - labor productivity, capital productivity-were significantly reduced in the agriculture of the republic. The volume of production does not grow, with the growth of the capital and the number of employees. And at this time, the basis of the republic's agriculture was made up of collective and state enterprises, which were provided with various benefits in lending and financing. There are significant losses at all stages of their production activities, and this is the most important sign of their economic inefficiency.

There is no doubt that there are no such losses either in farms or in the household plots of the population. However, in the process of reorganization of the state farm-old system, its breaking is unacceptable, and a gradual step-by-step transformation is required, until the new forms of farming in rural areas are able to provide the republic with food and industrial crops without interruption.

But even during the transition period, they must undergo transformation: they will decrease in size, switch to economic and commercial settlement relations, and temporarily use rental relations.

As the market economy strengthens, socio-economic relations will be simplified. Dehkan (farmer) farms and their cooperative associations will become the mode that most meets the requirements of the market and gains its predominance in agriculture. This is confirmed by the experience of many countries with developed

market economies and the results of scientific research. These cooperatives should combine the functions of material and technical support of dehkan (farmer) and small collective farms, processing of agricultural products, and its implementation. Certain types of activities of the cooperative should be the objects of its accounting. In these areas, the accounting should reflect the costs produced in the cooperative, the financial results and their distribution.

The formation and functioning of dehkan farms are inextricably linked with the organization of accounting. Accounting information about business activities is the main source for making operational management decisions. However, the accounting support for the activities of dehkan (farmer) farms is still in the formation stage. The practice of organizing accounting shows a variety of approaches to solving this problem. One dehkan (farm) farm uses the registers recommended for small enterprises for accounting, while others keep records of their activities in adapted books. The published recommendations differ significantly from each other in the methods of solving accounting problems, in particular, the use of accounting registers, the maintenance of accounting accounts, and other issues.

All this variety of approaches to the organization of accounting in dehkan farms allowed us to accumulate some positive experience in the technology of the accounting process. However, in this experiment, the technique of the accounting process, unfortunately, was in many ways ahead of the methodology of its management, which significantly complicated accounting, made it more time-consuming and in some cases an unsolvable task.

In our opinion, at present, the results of scientific research and the accumulated

experience of accounting in dehkan (farmer) farms allow us to create an accounting system that meets modern requirements and specific features of this area in order to achieve the following goals:

- minimum labor intensity of the accounting process;
- simplicity, clarity and accessibility;
- completeness of the reflection of the accounting object;
- timeliness of data generation for management decision-making;
- the unity of the principles of building registers and the order of keeping records.

In our opinion, accounting in dehkan (farm) farms, small in number of employees and small in volume of production, should be built according to a simple and accessible system without the use of accounting accounts and the method of double entry. This does not mean that a double entry of a business transaction for accounting objects is unacceptable. Technically, this can be accomplished by simply writing applied registers on two interconnected accounting objects.

The organization of accounting in cooperative or large dehkan farms, of course, should be entrusted to the accountant. It will not be difficult for him to develop a work plan for specific business conditions, determine the correspondence of accounts and make appropriate entries in the accounting registers.

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